

THE PASTORAL COUNSELLORS

JOURNAL *of* **NIGERIAN ASSOCIATION OF PASTORAL COUNSELLORS**

In collaboration with
Department of Religious and Intercultural Studies
and
Department of Guidance and Counselling
LEAD CITY UNIVERSITY, IBADAN, NIGERIA

VOL. 3. MAY 2024

ISSN: PRINT 2971-5199 ONLINE 2971-5202

Editors in Chief
Professor Samson Fatokun
Professor Donald A. ODELEYE

Managing Editors
Professor Isaiah ABOLARIN
Olabisi T. Precious KILLIAN PhD

Corresponding Editor
Adebayo Ola AFOLARANMI PhD

Pastoral Counselling and Domestic Violence in Nigeria: The Way Forward

Olusegun Augustus HARMONA, PhD
segunharmona@gmail.com, +2348033974197

Sarah Kehinde HENMAUGO
kehindesarah@yahoo.com, +2348034803967

Abstract

Pastoral counselling plays a pivotal role in addressing various challenges confronting human beings in the society; be it social, economic, religious and political. There is no gainsaying the fact that in the midst of problems, man needs counselling to serve as succor to the challenges of life. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of psychotherapy that uses spiritual and psychological resources in providing services for people. A close look at the Nigerian society today reveals that the family institution has lost its sacrosanctity as the foundation of the society. An average Nigerian family is faced with various forms of domestic violence that have led to severe injury, deformity and sometimes death. The focus of this paper is to unravel the roles of Pastoral Counseling in curbing domestic violence in the family. Analytical, historical and exegetical methodologies are employed. The findings revealed that domestic violence is caused by factors such as poverty, transfer of aggression and other related factors. The paper recommends effective and proper counseling for families in order to reduce the frequency of domestic violence.

Keywords: Pastoral Counseling, Domestic Violence, Family, Psychotherapy

Introduction

Domestic violence has become a common occurrence in Nigeria contemporary time. A critical look at the society reveals that cases of domestic violence are on the high side and has cut across all facets of the Nigerian society, regardless of age, tribe, religion and social status. Domestic violence takes many forms which include physical, sexual, emotional and mental. In Nigeria, domestic violence is traditionally committed against females. Common forms of violence against women include; rape, acid attacks, molestation, beating and verbal abuse. It is estimated that approximately one in every three women in Nigerian family suffers domestic violence and intimate partner violence from the hands of those who claim to love them. This is not to say that men do not also suffer domestic violence from women (Adekoya,2020). However, there are stories and videos on social media indicating that women are predominantly impacted by domestic violence. A good example is the case of the popular Gospel singer, late Mrs Osinachi Nwachukwu amongst others.

It is important to point out that domestic violence becomes rampant in our society because most victims still shy away from reporting cases of domestic violence to appropriate authorities, due to cultural factors and fear of stigmatization (Afolabi,2022). It is against this background that the researchers intend to examine the role of pastoral counselling in curbing domestic violence in Nigerian family.

The Concept of Pastoral Counselling

Pam (2013) describes pastoral counselling as a type of counselling or psychotherapy where in knowledge and standards stemming from the disciplines of theology and the behavioural sciences are utilized in working with people, couples, families, other sets of people, and cultural systems to reach a place of healing and development. Also, Odeleye (2017) sees pastoral counselling as a helping relationship in which a trained therapist (pastor or minister) assists individuals, couples and families resolve their emotional, relational and psychosocial issues, utilizing the Bible as primary manual. Pastoral counselling is a unique form of counselling which utilizes spiritual and psychological capital to help individuals to understand possible options to attain the balanced life. Odeleye (2022) pointed out that pastoral counseling is a therapeutic relationship between a congruent, stable and coordinated pastoral counselor and an incongruent, disturbed and confused counselee.

The American Association of pastoral counselling (1988) defines pastoral counseling as a unique form of psychotherapy which uses spiritual resources as well as psychological understanding for healing and growth. It is provided by certified pastoral counselors, who are not only mental health professionals but who have also had in-depth religious and theological training. It is imperative to point out that pastoral counseling is a specialized type of “pastoral care”. Pastoral care is derived from the biblical image of a shepherd who expresses concern for persons in trouble or distress. The word ‘pastor’ literally means shepherd, nurturer, watchman, carer. In this sense, pastors have a divine mandate to watch over spirit, soul and body of individuals and families committed to their care.

From the above conception of pastoral counseling, it is obvious that pastoral counselling is a humanitarian service/services rendered by trained pastors to people that are faced with challenges of life ranging from bereavement, trauma, personality disorder, spiritual depression, marital issues, mental health and so on.

Some Principles of Pastoral Counselling

Odeleye (2022) identifies some principles which every pastoral counselor needs to master in order to ensure optimal performance in his ministry. They are as follows:

- i. **Indepth Knowledge of the Bible:** The Bible is the inspired words of God. It is God’s revelation to guide the effective functioning of the human race. The counsellor needs to take the Bible as an integral part of his life before he can function effectively as a pastoral counselor.
- ii. **Prayer and Meditation:** A lifestyle of prayer and communion with the Holy Spirit should be the hallmark of a pastoral counsellor. A prayerful life will enable the counsellor to grow in grace and in the knowledge of His Lord and savior Jesus Christ. In addition to this, the counsellor should be able to meditate on the word of God. One of the keys to making success in therapy is the ability to meditate on the word of God for spiritual guidance.
- iii. **Pragmatic Preaching and Teaching:** The pastoral counsellor should make the pulpit the starting point of his work. The pastor or counselor should make his/her preaching

relevant to the needs of the people. It is assumed that not all issues will be addressed in a one-to-one situation, therefore the pastor should be able to proffer solutions to human problems in the course of preaching and teaching.

- iv. **Maintaining Confidentiality:** The counselor should be careful to keep all information the client gives to them in confidence. By this, the counselor earns the respect of the clients. Some information about the counselee are "classified information". It therefore behoves the counsellor to treat the information as such. This demands some degree of maturity.
- v. **Empathy:** Empathy is the ability to place oneself in the shoes of others. It is the ability to share the feelings of others. The counsellor needs to demonstrate Christ love in the course of helping people to solve their problems. In this wise, the counsellor shares the burden of the counselee.
- vi. **Experiencing the New Birth:** Pastoral counselling is not only based on the knowledge of psychology or academic qualifications. The pastoral counselor must be a firm believer in Christ and must be born again. The counsellor needs to have experience the salvation of God through our Lord Jesus Christ. He needs to be energized by the power of the word of God and the Holy Spirit.
- vii. **Fruit of the Spirit:** The counselor should exhibit the fruit of the Holy Spirit as enunciated in Galatians 5: 22-23. Love, Joy, peace, long suffering, gentleness, goodness, faith, meekness, temperance etc. lack of the fruit of spirit will dissuade the pastor from performing his duties as a counselor. It will be difficult for him to have compassion towards others.
- viii. **Attentive Listening:** The counsellor should be a good listener. It is fundamental for a spiritual counselor to possess the ability to listen to others with rapt attention. The counsellor should be a lover of humanity. Active listening conveys to clients that they are valued. However, listening involves every part of the body.

Biblical Foundation to Pastoral Counselling

There are no direct sayings on pastoral counselling in the Bible. However, there are allusions to counselling in the Old and New Testaments. The Christian's basis for counselling is nothing other than the scriptures. The bible makes it clear that God is in search of bringing healing, a holistic healing to the groaning creation (Ezammo, 2005).

Pastoral Counselling in the Old Testament

The care of God towards His creatures is visible in the creation story as presented in the Book of Genesis. The presence of a God who is active in the affairs of man is everywhere assumed. He demonstrates his act of love and kindness to all creatures. Genesis 1:27 asserts that man is made in the image and likeness of God. This is corroborated in Psalm 8:5 where man is described as "little less than God". In the anthropology of the Jewish scripture, all aspects of persons, not just their minds or spirits, are perceived as created in the divine image (Howard, 1984).

In the book of Exodus, when Moses was leading the Israelites through the wilderness, he was advised by Jethro his father-in-law, who himself was a priest to appoint helpers to share the work

of counseling the people (Exodus 18:1-2). This underscores the importance of counselling in the Old Testament scriptures. Also, the prophets performed the role of counsellors. Aside from interceding and calling the people to repentance, their fundamental role was to proclaim the word of God to the people. They reveal God's plan to the people who came for help. The prophets stood as mediators between God and the people by intervening in their personal problems. A good example is the case of Isaiah and Hezekiah where the prophet demonstrated personal empathy towards the king.

The Psalms are also reflections of human emotional experiences that are valuable for pastoral counselling. Feelings such as resentment, anxiety, despair on one hand and gratitude, serenity, confidence and joy on the other. The Psalms is therefore meant to encourage the development of positive feelings in the midst of life challenges. Psalms 23 for example emphasize the 'shepherding role' of the counselor.

Pastoral Counselling in the New Testament

There are lots of allusions to pastoral care and counseling in the New Testament especially in the life and ministry of Jesus. The New Testament writers used different Greek words to describe the various aspects of counselling. The words "Nouthesia" (giving advice or instruction), "paraklese" (to exhort, comfort, encourage, strengthen), "paramytheomai" (to cheer up, to encourage) and so on. From these Greek words, one can deduce that the word "counselling" contains many ideas depending upon the sort of help needed, and the aim of the counselor (Harold, 1989).

The Gospel of John describes Jesus' purpose of coming as being so that people could have "life in all its fullness" (John 10:10). The fullness here referred to "wholeness". Despite human limitations and brokenness, Jesus is a sure guarantor of our wholeness. Jesus as a model counselor had a deep psychic insight to read human mind. His conversation with the Samaritan woman is a good example. All through his ministry, he had compassion and showed love and care for people.

In the Book of Acts, the deacons were anointed to provide social support and care for widows in the early church. Also, in Acts 20:28 Paul admonishes the church elders to keep watch over themselves and all the flocks which the Holy Spirit has made them overseer. "Be shepherds of the Church of God, which he bought with his own blood". Also, in 1 Peter 5:2, Apostle Peter encouraged the elders to be shepherds of God's flock that is under their care, watching them not because they must, but because they are willing, as God wants them to be; not pursuing dishonest gain, but eager to serve. In the Epistles, Pastors are listed among other ministers (apostles, prophets, teachers and evangelist), for which Christ gave the gifts "to equip the saints for the work of ministry, for building up the body of Christ" (Ephesians 4:12)". From the above analysis, it is evident that pastoral care and counseling has its root from the Bible.

The Family

The family is a group of persons united by the ties of marriage, blood, or adoption, constituting a single household and interacting with each other in their respective social position usually those of spouses, parents, children and siblings (Alan, 2023). Basically, the family consists of two married adults, usually a man and a woman along with their offspring. This is known as the nuclear family. It is the basic social unit of the society. The family performs various roles for its

members. Some of the roles are; the provision of emotional and psychological security, rearing and socialization of children, provision of food, shelter, clothing, education and physical security for its members.

In most cultures, the family is patriarchal or male-dominated. However, the modern family that emerged after the Industrial Revolution is different from the earlier mode. The patriarchal posture of the family gave way to equality between the sexes. Family responsibility became a shared activity between the husband and the wife. The emancipation of women in the 19th and 20th centuries changed married dramatically, particularly in connection with prosperity and economic status. By the mid-20th century, most western countries had enacted laws establishing the equality between spouses. However, at the beginning of the 21st century, family notion has become complicated by calls for the acceptance of same-sex marriages and non-traditional family settings.

The average Nigerian family is made up of the father, mother and the children (nuclear family). In addition, the extended family system is still rampant in Nigeria like any other African countries. Despite the fact that the western lifestyle is slowly sipping into the Nigerian community, the issue of marriage or even the family system at large is not a private one, these two institutions are rarely established without the interference of the extended family members (Caldwell & Orubuloye, 1991). It is important to point out that in Nigeria (like other African countries), men are still dominant in private and public life. According to Ogundipe-Leslie (1994) 'the ideology that men are naturally superior to women In all areas, affects the modern-day organization of societal structures'.

Emphasis has always been placed on the male especially in the family system; mainly because the families in Nigeria are patrilineal, the males are seen as continuity of both family names and lineage. Women are generally seen as playing a second fiddle, with limited freedom. She is mostly restricted to child bearing and household duties.

Domestic Violence in Nigeria

The average Nigerian family is beset with so many problems ranging from poverty, infidelity, alcoholism, barrenness, pressure at workplace, financial problem and so on (Monday, 2010). The focus of this paper is the issue of domestic violence among Nigerian families. There is no gain saying the fact that domestic violence is a pervasive issue that affects the societies worldwide, with Nigeria being no exception. This silent pandemic has continued to erode the social fabric of Nigeria, leaving countless individuals, particularly women and children traumatized.

United Nations (1993) defines domestic violence as a pattern of behaviours in any relationship that is used to gain or maintain power and control over an intimate partner which could be physical, sexual, emotional, economic or psychological actions or threat of actions that influence another person. Also, section 18(g) of Lagos State domestic violence law defines domestic violence to include physical abuse, sexual abuse, exploitation including but not limited to rape, incest, and sexual assault, starvation, emotional, verbal and psychological abuse, economic abuse and exploitation; intimidation, harassment, hazardous attack... etc (Morohunfola, 2021).

Recent studies reveal that domestic violence is on the increase in Nigeria. According to a study commissioned by the Ministry of Women's Affairs and Social Development and the United

Nation's Population Fund (UNPA), 28% of Nigerian women aged 25-29 have experienced some form of physical violence since age 15. Also, according to the National Bureau of Statistics (2019), 30% of Nigerian women aged 15-49 have experienced physical violence, while 68% have encountered emotional, economic or sexual abuse. However, it is important to note that it is not only women that suffer domestic violence in Nigeria. Researches have also shown that men are also subjected to domestic violence. It is recorded that out of a total of 48 victims of domestic violence in Nigeria, 10.4% were males. However, these figures are undoubtedly underreported, as victims are faced with the barriers of cultural stigmas, fear of retribution and lack of trust in the legal system.

The causes of domestic violence in Nigeria include factors such as; gender inequality, harmful cultural practices, poverty, lack of education etc. The persistent adherence to patriarchal norms and beliefs contribute significantly to domestic violence against women. Moreover, harmful practices such as child marriage, female genital mutilation enhance these nefarious acts. Coupled with the above is the fact that the Nigerian judicial system is not robust enough to combat the menace of domestic violence.

Some Cases of Domestic Violence

There are numerous cases of domestic violence in recent times. According to the Lagos State Domestic and Sexual Violence Agency (DSVA, 2022), the agency received over 4,800 cases of domestic violence from September, 2021 to July, 2022. A strong case of domestic violence in Nigeria is that of a popular gospel singer, Osinachi Nwachukwu who died after suffering from alleged domestic violence from her husband, Peter Nwachukwu. Similarly, a man named David Idibie was arrested for allegedly beating his wife Julianah Idibie to death at the Ajah area of Lagos State. In April, 2022, one Anulika Aguru, a mother of seven died in Ebonyi State following alleged domestic violence by her husband. These are few cases of reported domestic violence that has led to the death of the victims. It is pertinent to say that women are majorly the victims of domestic violence.

Impact of domestic violence

There are many negative impacts of domestic violence on individuals and the society. Firstly, domestic violence may cause serious injury and sometimes death to the victim. Even if it does not lead to death, it causes some psychological distress or trauma to the victim. It reduces the personality of the victim, and may also lead the victim to a state of depression. Secondly, domestic violence affects the emotional state of the children in the affected family. The children of the victims of domestic violence might become exposed to violence and other ungodly behaviours. In the aspect of education, such children may experience low academic performance because of lack of concentration. Thirdly, domestic violence is a dishonor to the family and the marriage institution. God instituted marriage as a means of companionship and togetherness. The man and the woman leave their parents to become one flesh. It is therefore pertinent to say that domestic violence is a crime against humanity

Pastoral Counselling and Domestic Violence

It should be noted that domestic violence and abuse can cause emotional disturbances such as self-hatred, guilt, despair, psychological trauma and self-annihilation. One should understand that a common symptom of mental disturbance is the loss of a sense of reality (Davies, 2014). In situations like that, pastoral counseling becomes necessary. The pastoral counsellor needs the knowledge of the spiritual and the emotional aspects of health as well as the socio-cultural structures, individual's psychological structures and social context. The pastoral counselor should understand the distress of the victim of domestic violence and should be eager to lead the victims out of the situation into right relationship with themselves, the world and God (Collin, 2003). An image from the Old Testament poetically describes this process: "For in the wilderness shall waters break out, and streams in the desert" (Isaiah, 35:7-10). In this passage, healing from emotional wounds is compared to the streams of water breaking out in the wilderness or desert to revive, bring relief and quench the thirst of a person going through emotional dryness, loneliness or pain (Davies 2014).

A pastoral counsellor is looked upon as a person of faith who is committed and trustworthy (Vanghan, 1987:17). He understands the value of God's power as a result, he needs the instrument of prayer to counsel the victim of domestic violence. Prayer can provide spiritual support for people suffering from anxiety and depression, by giving them a sense of belonging and comfort. Pastoral care and counseling should provide emotional support for survivors of domestic violence. According to Bay (2008), individuals who received pastoral care are better equipped both emotionally and spiritually. Pastoral counseling includes listening, understanding and building a trusting relationship, as well as treating the person with compassion, dignity and respect (Newett, 2009).

Amongst the various therapeutic methods used by pastoral counsellors in solving the problems of domestic violence, narrative counselling and logotherapy are identified as appropriate methods (Bigear, 2010). These two methods are compatible with religious themes such as 'hope' and 'new life'. In narrative method, the aim is for people to find hope. The stories of the past and memories are searched to discover meaning in life and the individual is guided to develop a new future story (Muller, 2010). In narrative pastoral counseling, the narrative of the individual is merged with the story of Christ. Logotherapy method is a model of psychotherapy which focuses on the meaning of life. It allows the counselor to enter the counsellee's emotional sphere and then bring about a new meaning in life (Frank, 2004).

The point of departure between psychologists and pastoral counsellors is that psychologists assist people with troubled lives and dysfunctional relationships to move to a healthier, functioning life and relationships while pastoral counselors for instance make use of biblical themes and spiritual devices such as prayer. Survivors of domestic violence need the services of pastoral counselors to handle the trauma caused by domestic violence.

Conclusion

This paper examines the relevance of pastoral counseling in addressing the menace of domestic violence in Nigeria. The researchers observed that domestic violence is one of the major social vices in the contemporary Nigeria society that has led to distress, emotional and psychological

trauma, despair, annihilation, hatred and loss of self-dignity in the lives of survivors. It was also discovered that women and children are majorly the victims of domestic violence when compared to the number of men. The paper therefore submits that pastoral counseling has a major role to play in helping the survivors to come out of the trauma of domestic abuse.

Recommendations

- i. Pastors and other church ministers should embark on effective marriage counseling for their members and those who approach them for marriage counseling.
- ii. Premarital seminars should be organized for youths in the church in order to take precautions before going into marriage.
- iii. The church should educate the people to seek for "safety" whenever they observe any form of domestic abuse in their marriages.
- iv. Pastoral counselors should adopt an effective, biblical base method of counseling the victims of domestic violence.
- v. Pastoral counselors should show the feeling of 'empathy' for survivors of domestic violence, in the process of counseling.
- vi. Pastoral counselors should be well equipped with the Bible and also be prayerful in their work of counseling the people.
- vii. Pastoral counselors should understand the principles of human psychology in order to make their job easier.
- viii. The pastoral counselor should endeavour to develop the skills of bringing hope to people that are experiencing the trauma of domestic violence.
- ix. Government should establish a strong judiciary system to address cases of domestic violence.
- x. Lastly, people should be educated on the need to cry out whenever they are being abused.

References

- Adekoya B.A (2020) Domestic Violence in the contemporary Nigeria Society. *Social Science and Human ethic.* 2(1) 22-49
- Afolabi P.O. (2022) Domestic Violence, Peace and Harmonious Living. *Humanities in the 21st Century* 1(2) 32-53
- Bay, P.S. and Beckham, D. et.al (2008). The Effects of Pastoral Care Services on Anxiety, Depression and Religious Problem Solving Styles. *Journal of Religion and Health.* 47(1): 57-69.
- Biggar, N. (2010). "The New Testament and Violence" *Studies in Christian Ethics.* 23(1), 73-80.
- Caldwell, J.C. & Orubuloye, I.O. (1991). The Destabilization of the Traditional Yoruba Sexual System. In *Population and Development Review.* 17(2), 229-262.
- Ezammo, M. (2005). *An Introduction to Pastoral Care and Counseling.* Delhi: ISPCK. 132.
- Frank, V. (2004). *Man's Search for Meaning.* London: Rider Press. P. 46.
- Howard, C. (1984). *Basic Types of Pastoral Care and Counseling.* Resources for Healing and Growth. Nashville: Abingdon Press. 53.
- Monday, V.O. (2010). The Future of the Family in Nigeria. *Nigerian Journal of Research and Production.* 16(1), 1-9.

- Morohunfola, A. (2021). Domestic Violence in Nigeria: The Laws and their Limitations. Retrieved from www.pastoralcare.com
- Muller, J. (2010). International Pastoral Care and Counselling. Unpublished Reader, Cape Town Baptist Seminary.
- Nathaniel, S. (2022). DSVA Received over 4800 Cases of Domestic/Sexual Violence in 10 Months. Retrieved from www.channelstv.com
- Odeleye, D.A. (2014). Biblical Spiritual Parenting: Way out of Nigeria's Logjam. *Journal of Educational Research* 2(4): 21-22.
- Odeleye, D.A. (2022). Overview of Pastoral Counseling. *Journal of Nigerian Association of Pastoral Counselors*.
- Pam, M.S. (2013). "Pastoral Counseling". <https://psychologydictionary.org/pastoral.counseling>
- The American Association of Pastoral Counselors (1988). "Journey of a Pastoral Counselor". *Journal of Pastoral Care and Counseling*. 42(3). Pp. 10-31.
- United Nations (1993). "Declaration on the Elimination of Violence Against Women". New York: UN.
- Vaughan, R.P. (1987). *Basic Skills for Christian Counselors: An Introduction for Pastoral Ministers*. New York: Paulist Press.